

ANITA DESAI'S NOVEL "CRY, THE PEACOCK" AND FEMININE SENSIBILITY

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Abstract

The most common theme the novels of Anita Desai is the complexity of human relationship, particularly the man-woman relationship. She writes mostly about the miserable plight of women suffering under their insensitive and inconsiderable husbands, fathers and brothers. So the man-woman relationship brings characters into alienation, withdrawal, loneliness, isolation and lack of communication that frequently occurs in her novels. Most of her novel's protagonists are alienated from the world, from society, from families, from parents and even from their ownelves because they are sensitive, high stung individuals. When these characters have to face alienation, they become rebels. Tension, worries, depression, disappointment, anxiety and fear become their lot and they lose their sense of sanity and mental poise, for example Maya in Cry.

Keywords: *Sensibility, Feminine, fictitious, alienation, legacy.*

Woman as a class, as a separate entity, as a category, has been for centuries not recognized as a person in her own rights. Excluded from vital experiences as Simone de Beauvoir rightly points out "what peculiarly signalizes the situation of woman is that she-a free and autonomous being like all human creatures nevertheless finds herself living in a world where men compel her to assume the status of the Other" . She aptly raises pertinent questions such as: "How can a human being in woman's situation attain fulfillment? How can independence be recovered in a state of dependency? What circumstances limit women's liberty and how can they be overcome?" .

The focus of this study is to context these questions in the writing of writers belonging to two continents. As a diasporic Indian writer, having lived in two or more countries, Anita Desai had confessed that, "she feels about India as an Indian, she thinks as an outsider" . As individuals and writers uprooted from their native grounds, either by chance or choice, these

women writers, who infuse their characters with notions of powerlessness, helplessness and as victims of estrangement, isolation and alienation, may have probably frequently experienced these emotions themselves. In general terms, alienation describes “a situation in which someone separates from something” (Fischer). This ‘something’ is a point where the specific perspective, towards the main concept, diverge. Peter L. Berger opines that “the essence of all alienation is the imposition of a fictitious inexorability upon the humanity constructed world”, by which “choices become destiny”. Besides the general conception of alienation, it is closely allied with humanistic sciences such as philosophy, psychology and sociology.

Alienation is endemic to human existence. It is a state wherein a person fails to maintain a sense of identity, leading to a disintegration of his psychophysical system. A state of alienation exists when a person is unable to identify himself either with his self or with the society. When a person lacks an identity, it is said that he is alienated. But a sense of non-alienation exists in proportion to the existence of sense of identity. No person is entirely lacking in any of the aforesaid conditions. Hence, all individuals are neither totally alienated nor entirely non-alienated. Man is a machine. To have an identity, he must make a persistent endeavor to keep the machine going satisfactorily. When he is unable to function satisfactorily, it is said that he is alienated. But alienation is more profound and disturbing in women than in men.

The most defined and accepted concept of alienation is Melvin Seeman’s socio-psychological definition presented in his research paper *On the meaning of Alienation* (1959). Pointing out ‘alienation’ as the major factor leading to detachment or ‘estrangement’, he offers five major modes of alienation such as:

1. Powerlessness: the individual's feeling of helplessness and losing control over one’s life, and that his efforts do not positively influence the out growths.
2. Meaninglessness: the uncertainty of the individual on his beliefs, decisions and actions; a state of hopelessness about future events.
3. Normlessness: an individual's feelings that socially unaccepted behaviours are the means of reaching likely goals.
4. Social-Isolation: assuming less value for socially and normally praised aims or beliefs which leads one to be separated from a group or the society.
5. Self-Estrangement: a disconnection between the actualized self and the ideal, or ought to be self; a state of losing natal meaning of self. Seeman also referred to the concept of cultural

estrangement, which can be related to social-isolation as society is the place where the culture is practiced. Alienation may roughly be classified as: alienation from others, alienation from work, a feeling of powerlessness and alienation from culture. According to psychology, a six level hierarchy of motives determine human behavior:-

- 1) physiological needs
- 2) security and safety needs
- 3) need for love affection and feelings of belonging,
- 4) competence prestige and esteem
- 5) selffulfillment
- 6) curiosity and need to understand. If these needs remain unsatisfied, the individual is prone to pangs of loneliness, rootlessness, ostracism and likely to be maladjusted and a victim of psychological disorders.

Female alienation is a theme that has been portrayed and discussed threadbare by many writers. Alienation that of women may be defined as a dislocation, a separation from their family both mentally and physically. It is an estrangement from the existing values and society. A sort of neurotic phobia over takes them. As a result, their mental health gets destabilized. Such high state of distress in women is instantiative. They search for the deep causes of alienation and the magnitude of loneliness increases disastrously. A woman's situation is precarious as time sweeps, whereby abandoned by her family which teases and taints her and the society which taunts her she becomes frozen. Such condition often results in expressing greater symptoms involving anxiety and withdrawal known as internalizing disorders. More such internalizing disorders are depression, fear, obsessions, psychosomatic complaints and schizoid features. All these internalizing syndromes are associated with the traditional categories of neurotic and physiological disorders. Divorced women are generally faced with gossip in all its split forms in a society. Such depressed and broken persons need something emotional, through attachment, love, compassion, advice and consent etc. Sometimes divorcees become victim of emotional discrepancy. They become friendless or are forced to rebuild their own alienated world, unable to face severe problems. In a woman when both the sexual and physiological aspects, forcibly interrupt, she faces a crises. She is pushed into a variety of insulting shafts because of her ambiguous status. However virtuous might be a woman but the divorcee in her is considered a fair game by the community. Wounded pride is an almost inevitable consequence of divorce and divorce impairs the self-feeling in several ways.

1. The failure to make a success of marriage regardless of the fault of the spouse is a serious reflection upon the self.
2. Friends may take sides and blame one mate for the failure of the marriage thus contributing to the injured ego-feeling of the guilty one.
3. The residual social attitude towards divorce, with its implication of failure and even deliberate moral turpitude, still further undermines the ego of the divorced person.

Indian women novelists did not face acute cultural obstacles and socio-economic barriers, they were however grappling with a foreign language—English - the legacy, a left behind the colonial rule, and learning its intricacies in order to employ it to express all matters that was 'native'. In keeping with the literary potential of their western sister novelists, Indian women novelists did persist in using the novel as a vehicle for exhibiting the 'deepest' human experiences and feelings. Keenly aware of the problems and hardships of women living in a traditional society. They strove to pack their novels with elements of realism and authenticity. They dealt with various socio-political economic and cultural issues. Other themes included issues of caste, class, sex, gender, race, identity crisis and other contemporary societal themes, besides the east west encounter, cross cultural problems, immigration and expatriate issues were dealt within the novels. The women writers were determined to create a 'literature of their own', "a canon of works", one that was not an equal or alternative to male canon of masterpieces, but one that would air their voices, their experiences, point of view, values, originality, diversity and creativity. The theme of alienation became one of the powerful devices in women's hands, to exclusively focus on women's problems and dilemmas in coping up with this modernist malaise.

As Walter Kaufmann remarks, "whether we choose to speak of alienation or not, the experiences widely associated with that term are often held to be distinctive characteristics of our time". There are numerous alienated characters in male texts who drift in and out in modern literature. The artist as an alien, figures in James Joyce's *Portrait Of The Artist As A Young Man*, the Negro or Jew as an outsider in Ralph Ellison's *Invisible Man* and Saul Bellow's *Herzog*, the outsider as a sensitive adolescent in Salinger's *Catch The Rye*, Camus's *Meursault* and Kafka's 'K' are serious exercises in depicting the modern conditions which defy man's confusion, frustration, disintegration and estrangement. Alienation has also frequently been a recurrent theme in existentialist literature and absurd drama.

Among these brilliant galaxy of writers, who have explored the theme of female alienation are two writers, Anita Desai an Indian, who has now migrated abroad, and is still actively

writing and the other writer selected is the Afro-American Toni Morrison, a black writer, writing on issues that cut across all human structured barriers. What yokes these two writers across culture, is their stark but realistic and authentic portrayal of women alienated due to various reasons: alienated from the self, family, community, society, environment, circumstances etc.

Initially Indian Writing In English was critiqued for its lack of quality and quantity but the emergence of the three literary giants: Mulk Raj Anand, Raja Rao and R.K. Narayan gave a powerful impetus to the writing of fiction. Gradually scores of women writers began to enter the vast patriarchal dominated literary area and started making a "room" for themselves. Writers like Anita Desai, Nayantara Sahgal, Kamala Markandaya and others carried the Indian Fiction in English to a height that it deserved, just as these writers were craving for a literary identity. Among the prominent themes that attracted the Indian women writers were the theme of alienation and quest for self-identity. In many instance both the writers and their fictional characters faced the same space of thinking this sense of anomie, of having no roots. Inevitably this sense of loss of identity as Okin opines leading to "the loss of identity, often results in alienation"

This study as it explores the theme of alienation found inscribed in the novels of Anita Desai, outlines the critical output in this specific theme of alienation. "Alienation of women characters in Anita Desai's novels" by Dr.C.V George, traces alienation as a thematic motif in Desai's fiction. The article on "Heroines of Toni Morrison and Anita Desai: A Cross-cultural perspective" by Bharathi. A. Parikh is an article which has direct relevance to this topic of research. " The theme of suffering in the select fictions of Anita Desai" By A. Namasivayam, "Cry The Peacock, A study in the theme of Alienation" by B.D. Pandey, "Woman's striving for a meaningful life in Anita Desai's Cry, The Peacock", by Vinod Kumar Maheshwari, " The psychic Trauma in Anita Desai's Cry, The Peacock" by V. Sunitha, "The Theme of marital discord in Anita Desai's Cry The peacock", by S.P. Swain "Treatment of Neurosis in Cry, The Peacock" by Q.F. Inamdar, . "The poetics of feminism in Anita Desai's Cry The Peacock" by N. D. Chandra, " The Alienated self of Maya: A Study of Anita Desai's Cry, The Peacock" by S.P Swain, "Claustrophobia in Anita Desai's Cry The Peacock: From Defeat to Disaster," by Deepthi Chauchan, are a few articles which focus exclusively on the themes of alienation, neurosis, pain, suffering, psychic trauma in Anita Desai's Cry The Peacock. Other sources such as "The lonely voyage: Feminine psyche in Anita Desai's Cry The Peacock" by Prabhat Kumar Pandeya, "Feminism and Anita Desai's Cry The Peacock and Where shall We

Go This Summer by M. Mani Meiter, "Women Lost: Cry The Peacock, Chapter II - The predicament of Women protagonist in Anita Desai's Novels" by N. Sethuraman, "Separation and psyche in Anita Desai's Cry, The Peacock", by Dr. M. Rajeswar, "Anita Desai's Cry The Peacock : A Vindication of the Feminine" by Som. P. Sharma and Kamal N. Awasthi, " The illusions of Maya: Feminine consciousness in Anita Desai's Cry The Peacock by Ani Lowary Weir, "Anita Desai - Cry, The Peacock chapter 24 studies in Indo-Anglican literature", ed by Dr Krishna Nanda Joshi and Dr. B. Shyamala Rao, again focuses on feminism, female psyche, feminine consciousness, etc. Some of the general studies on Anita Desai focus on aspects such as "Sense and Sensitivity of women characters in the Novels of Anita Desai" by Rita Roy, "Memorable characters in Indian writing in English" by P.K Kumaresan, "Anita Desai" by R.S Sharma, "Alienation to Existentialism.

A Study of Anita Desai's novels" by Shashipal are some which focus on generic themes. Martial discord is discussed in "Dialectics of marital polarization in Anita Desai's Cry The Peacock", by S.P .Swain. Anita Desai's Voices In The City is analyzed by Madhavi Latha Agarwal in "Anita Desai in Voices In The City", "Images of alienation-A study of Anita Desai's novels" by Dr. S. P Swain. "The Alienated self in the novels of Anita Desai" by R.S Pathak, "Anita Desai and the wounded self", by V.V.N Rengachari Prasad, "Fate and Fatalism in Anita Desai's Cry The Peacock" by Dr. S.S Rengachari, "Anita Desai : The Novelist" by Madhusudan Prasad, "The Ailing Aliens" by Kalpana Wadrekar, "From Self-Alienation to selfidentification: A study of Anita Desai's novels" by S.P. Swain and P. M. Nayak, "Alienation in Indian Novel in English" by L. Manjula Davidson are a few articles which focus on themes of alienation from differing perceptions. The comparative aspects is dealt with by S. Indira in "Exploration of inner space: Anita Desai and Bharati Mukherjee" "Existential Dilemma in Anita Desai's Voices In The City", by Dr.Poonam Rani Gupta, "Anita Desai- Alienation in "Voices In The City" by Madhavi Lata Agrawal, "Relationship Dilemma in Anita Desai's novels" by Behnaz Alipour Kaskari, explores the Existential conflict and the relationship dilemma. "Anita Desai's Where Shall We Go This Summer?: A Psychoanalytical study" by Dr. Mr. Mani Meiter, "Where Shall We Go This Summer? - Sita's incarcerated self", by S.P Swain and P.M. Nayak's, "The woman who sailed Back: Where Shall We Go This Summer". "The reverse patterns of journey in Anita Desai's Cry the Peacock and Where Shall We Go This Summer?" by Dr.Sanjay Kumar and "Light and Darkness - The Futile Quest for a Harmonious Blend in Anita Desai's Where Shall We Go This Summer?" by T. Mathukal analyses the theme of alienation. Other critics like Arvind M.

Nawak, B. Chitra, Amit Saha, S. Sujatha, Basavaraj Naikar, M. Sivaram Krishna, Ruth K. Rasen Wasser, Usha Bande, D. K. Pably, are a few who have written elaborately on various aspects of alienation in Anita Desai's novels.

Findings:

In *Cry, The Peacock*, Maya is alienated from Gautama, who is pragmatic, unromantic, unsentimental and believes in 'detachment on every count', while Maya, on the other hand, is highly sensitive, gifted with poetic imagination and emotional. Their incompatible temperaments make it difficult for them to have a warm and harmonious relationship and pave way for their estrangement. Maya rightly says, "Our marriage was based upon nobility forced upon us from outside, and therefore neither true nor lasting. It was broken repeatedly, and repeatedly the pieces were picked up and put together again" (CTP 51). By relating Maya's neurosis to her marriage, Anita Desai transforms artistically the conventional story of marital disharmony into a moving study of the psyche of Maya, who seeks love, sympathy and understanding, suffers intensely every moment. By marrying a man twice her age, Maya probably had already minimized her chances for a good husband-wife relationship. She painfully becomes aware of her 'loneliness in this house' and whispers 'I am alone'.

The death of dog has made Maya realize her sense of alienation. She regards the death of dog Toto as the biggest tragedy leading to alienation from her husband for it is something natural for Gautama. She blames her husband for all her problems. The person who has realized her true identity will never do so. The fundamental law of the Universe is that one is responsible for one's problems and miseries. Blaming on others alienates a person from his real self and consequently from God and his creation. Hence alienation means isolation from one's own soul. Maya feels the agony of alienation sending her towards meaningless life which she does not want to lead at all. The aspect of alienation that springs from constant neglect or rejection and the failure to communicate or understand is realistically portrayed in the sensitive individual, Maya. This idea of alienation develops into the next phase. i.e. self-alienation, observed in *Nanda Kaul* and *Raka*. This kind of situation more or less prevails in Desai's first novel *Cry, The Peacock*.

The *Peacock*, *Sita* in *Where Shall We Go This Summer?* and *Nanda Kaul* in *Fire On The Mountain*. Some characters like Maya and *Nanda Kaul* are unable to reconcile to alienation and meet with a tragic end. Most of her protagonists are alienated ones. She portrays her characters as individuals "facing singlehanded, the ferocious assaults of existence".

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